

Biomarker Analytical Laboratories

RECETOX, Faculty of Science, Masaryk University, Czech Republic

Title: SOP to assemble and disassemble API source (OptaMax NG) and clean interface components (ion sweep cone, spray cone, ion transfer tube and O-ring) of Orbitrap Exploris 480.

Date: 2025-03-01

Version: version 1

Author: Štěpán Koudelka

Checked by: Žiža Tkalec

IMPORTANT

- Clean the inlet components prior to calibration or batch acquisition by MS.
- Use a new pair of lint- and powder-free gloves before starting each removal and cleaning.
- Use UCL/MS absolute isopropyl alcohol and water (Biosolve Chimie SARL), formic acid (p.a., Fluka).
- To manipulate or disassemble the API source and interface components, place the MS to Off Mode.
- Make sure that you do not introduce any scratches or surface abrasions by using inappropriate tools or handling the API source and interface components.
- Make a note about cleaning the API source interface components of the MS to the Logbook.
- SW: Xcalibur 4.7.69.37, Thermo Scientific for SII Xcalibur 1.7.0.468, Orbitrap Exploris Tune 4.3.458.15

To prepare the API source interface

1. Check there is no flow running to the API source of MS, if yes:
 - a) set the divert valve to waste (1-6 position) in Orbitrap Exploris Tune Application (Tune window), OR
 - b) turn off the Vanquish Duo LC pumps by Direct Control.
2. In the Tune window, place the MS to Off Mode.
3. Unscrew the tubing by ferule connecting the divert valve to the grounding union. After the API source cools to room temperature, remove it from the MS by unlocking the levers on both sides (Figure 1).

External surface of spray insert, the API source, and the entry of ion transfer tube can become hot enough to burn you therefore wait until cool down to room temperature before touching them.

Figure 1 The API source housing of the MS

To remove the ion sweep cone and the ion transfer tube with letterbox entry (D.I.S., PN 80500-20045)

Make sure you don't accidentally lift the release lever located at the top of API source which will vent the MS!

1. Remove the ion sweep cone by grasping its outer ridges and pulling it off smoothly.
2. Align the flat edges of custom removal tool with the flat edges on exposed tip of the ion transfer tube. Use the correct tool end, rotate by ¼-turn counterclockwise, then use the other tool end to remove it out of the API source interface. Inspect the O-ring located behind the ion transfer tube.

Figure 2 Showing API source interface components with release lever highlighted in red

To clean the spray cone and O-ring

1. Soak lint-free tissue (e.g., Kimwipes) in 50:50 isopropyl alcohol (IPA)/water solution and clean outside surface of the spray cone. If necessary, replace or clean the O-ring with methanol.

To clean the ion sweep cone

1. Clean the ion sweep cone with lint-free tissue soaked in 50:50 IPA/water solution. Sonicate it in 50:50 IPA/water solution (80 mL IPA + 80 mL water) in clean 250 mL beaker for 10 mins.
2. Sonicate the component in water for 10 mins and then in IPA for 10 mins.
3. Let it air-dry completely on a clean surface at aluminium foil in hood.

To clean the ion transfer tube

1. If there is extreme contamination, follow step 1. If not skip it and start with step 2.
 - a) Sonicate the ion transfer tube in 2% solution of alkaline detergent in water.
 - b) Rinse it thoroughly with a stream of tap water from all sides.(OR) Use alumina powder and wet lint-free tissue swab to smoothly remove contamination.
2. Sonicate the component in 50:50 IPA/water solution (30 mL IPA + 30 mL water) in clean 250 mL beaker for 10 mins.
3. Sonicate the component in water for 10 mins and then in IPA for 10 mins.
4. Let it air-dry completely on a clean surface at aluminium foil in hood. Replace the ion transfer tube if the bore becomes corroded or blocked.

Figure 3 Showing the API source interface and assembling the components

To assemble the API source interface components (Figure 3)

1. Following the O-ring replacement, check that it was installed properly.
2. Carefully insert the ion transfer tube (do not bend!) by the custom removal tool and rotate while inserting it to the final position.
3. Push the ion sweep cone back and make sure that it fits.
4. Assembly the API source housing to the MS and lock it on both sides.
5. Adjust the spray insert to position 1 or 2 for calibration or acquisition.
6. Screw the tubing via ferule connecting the divert valve (acquisition) or the syringe needle (calibration) to the grounding union.
7. Place the MS to Standby or On Mode.

Note: The used figures were obtained from Orbitrap Exploris Series (Thermo Fisher Scientific): Operating Manual and OptaMax NG Ion Source User Guide.